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Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in Selected Food Outlets, Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Most customers expect value for their money in the form of quality products and services. The study examines the relationship between quality products or services and customer satisfaction in selected food outlets in the Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The research design is the descriptive survey and data gathered through a well-structured questionnaire. The sample for the study consists of 120 literate individuals who are customers of selected food outlets in the Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos, drawn through the simple random technique. The questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection, measured on a 5-point Likert Scale. Data collected were analysed using the descriptive statistical techniques of Percentiles and Regression methods with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software for editing and encoding. The findings of the study revealed that quality service consistency has a significant relationship and effect on the sales volume ($r = 0.336$, $p < 0.05$) and that there is a significant relationship between staff etiquette and customer purchase intention ($r = 0.766$, $p < 0.05$). The study, however, recommended that food outlet owners should properly identify and anticipate the needs of the customers, maintain consistency of service quality with customer orders, ensure periodic staff training to enhance customer-service skills in active listening, empathy, complaints handling, role playing, teamwork and collaboration, upselling and closing thoughts, introduce modern safety techniques and excellent interpersonal relationships.

Keywords: Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality Consistency, Staff Etiquette, Purchase Intention

Introduction

Presently, the ever-increasing consumers' demand for quality food has left many fast food and restaurant owners in a dilemma. Product and service quality is the marketer's main positioning tool.

Restaurants and other food service providers compete fiercely in the food processing and supply industries. Customer satisfaction is essential for businesses to win over recurring business and client loyalty (Uddin, 2019). Service quality is a key factor in determining customer satisfaction. Studies have found a positive relationship between the five dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction (Ahmed et al., 2023; Nguyen, 2018). After getting or using a service, customers evaluate its quality immediately and compare their experiences to what they had anticipated. Perceptions of the anticipated service level determine levels of

satisfaction or discontent, the quality of the service, and the difference between these two (Ahmed et al., 2023; Nguyen, 2018; Uzir et al., 2021; Uddin, 2019).

Restaurants and other food service providers compete fiercely in the food processing and supply industries. Customer satisfaction is essential for businesses to win over recurring business and client loyalty (Uddin, 2019). Service quality is a key factor in determining customer satisfaction. Studies have found a positive relationship between the five dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction (Ahmed et al., 2023; Nguyen, 2018). It is claimed that customer satisfaction in a service factory is positively correlated with service quality and that service quality accurately reflects consumer satisfaction levels. After getting or using a service, customers evaluate its quality immediately and compare their experiences to what they had anticipated. Perceptions of the anticipated service level determine levels of satisfaction or discontent, the quality of the service, and the difference between these two (Ahmed et al., 2023; Nguyen, 2018; Uzir et al., 2021; Uddin, 2019).

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective is to examine the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in selected food outlets in the Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. investigate the effect of quality consistency on sales volume in selected food outlets in the Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.
- ii. examine the influence of staff etiquette on customer purchase intention in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does service quality consistency affect sales volume in selected food outlets in the Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria?
- ii. How does staff etiquette influence customer purchase intention in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Service Quality consistency has no significant relationship with the sales volume in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between staff etiquette and customer purchase intention in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Scope and Significance of the Study

The study was limited to all categories of numerous customers of selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The local government area was chosen because it enjoys the patronage of a large number of customers. However, the study is desirable for managers in the eatery business and organisations to imbibe the concept of standard products at a reasonable price, so that customers can start having the belief that they are now exchanging their money for standard service quality. When customers start seeing themselves as king, it will make them loyal to the menu of such food outlets. Again, the study will make

the managers of food outlets aware of the consequences of reducing the quality of their menu/food or services, thereby providing insights into the development and management of food outlets by designing strategies for better quality control.

Literature Review

Namkung & Jang (2007) described the quality of food as a concept that includes “taste, freshness, variety, healthy options, and temperature”. According to the study of Annaraud & Berezina (2020), food quality is an indispensable factor in the foodservice industry, it greatly affects customer satisfaction. It is also a “necessary condition” to meet the needs and expectations of customers, then make them feel satisfied (Peri, 2006).

Moreover, the research of Kedah, Ismail, Ahasanul, and Ahmed (2015) suggested that companies need to consider service quality as a vital issue and have specific strategies and plans to maintain and improve service quality.

Hawkins et al. (2010) also mentioned that “satisfaction leads to a number of positive outcomes”, including repeat purchases. East, Wright, & Vanhuele (2013) also showed that most firms are keen to increase satisfaction among customers because this is thought to retain customers. So, it is no wonder why so many firms attempt to create satisfied customers because they are much more profitable than occasional buyers or spend a large budget to build campaigns and events to attract new customers.

Measuring service quality is also challenging, as service quality assessment is conducted both during the service delivery process and after the service is completed (Nguyen, 2018). Organisations can obtain a bigger competitive advantage by providing higher levels of service quality; this is why service quality has been extensively explored in marketing and management literature (Su et al., 2022). Service quality is a vigorous factor for consumer-centric business as it is the prime factor for customer satisfaction (Kim, 2021; Uzir et al., 2021).

The SERVQUAL Model is used to measure and record the level of service quality that clients get in different service sectors, such as on-demand home service (Sivathanu, 2019), hotel businesses in Indonesia (Priyo, 2018), the life insurance industry in Malaysia (AI Halbusi et al., 2020), and restaurant businesses in Korea (Kim, 2019). Service quality has been found to have a positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction (Uzir et al., 2021). Food delivery from restaurant to dine in at home includes the app and web-based (UI and UX) user interface and user experience through timely and accurate order delivery, immediate customer support, trust in the platform, deliveryman, and customised service (Madhuritha & Nedumaran, 2025). By applying SERVQUAL, restaurants can identify areas where service quality falls short, make data-driven improvements, and enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the following industry (Arli, D. et al., 2024).

Consumption of quality food is vital to health and well-being. Ashakiran and Deepthi (2012) confirm that consumption of healthy food is one of the essential requirements for a long life. Unfortunately, today’s world has been adapted to a system of consumption of foods which has several adverse effects on health. These foods are known as junk. What makes food junk is that it contains high levels of refined sugar, white flour, trans fat and polyunsaturated fat, salt, and numerous food additives such as monosodium glutamate and tartrazine; at the same

time, it is lacking in proteins, vitamins, essential minerals, and fibre, among other healthy attributes (Ashakiran and Deepthi, 2012).

Evidently and indisputably, most of the contemporary fast-food outlets are associated with junk foods because of the profit motive. They are cheap and easy to prepare, easy to carry, purchase and consume. They have an attractive appearance based on the added food colourants and additives, which enhance flavour and texture. But one thing is sure and is sadly overlooked, that consumers want to enjoy their purchased food, they need quality food for healthy living and longevity. They are desirous of having value for the money spent on purchased food.

Liu and Jang (2009) found that food quality has the capacity to create a favourable preference for the firm's products, whereby consumers can differentiate the quality of its products from those of competitors. Physical evidence is the environment in which the service is delivered and where the firm and customer interact, and any tangible components that facilitate performance or communication of the service (Olannye, 2016). According to Bhasin (2018), how do you differentiate a premium food outlet from a regular food outlet? To create such differentiation, physical evidence is used.

Physical evidence, however, comprises the elements which are incorporated into a service to make it tangible and somewhat measurable, such as the ambience, layout and branding. At the same time, it helps in the positioning of the brand and targeting the right kind of customers. It is said that customers cannot assess the quality of service as it is an intangible performance. It is the customer's expectation that the physical environment of a firm should possess the quality attributes it seems to have, with a good sense of comfort and serenity. Olannye (2016) stated that service marketers must manage physical evidence effectively because potential customers use it to gauge service quality.

Theoretical Perspectives

The Dissonance Theory suggests that a person who expected a high-value product and received a low-value product would recognise the disparity and experience cognitive dissonance (Cardozzo, 1965). That is, the disconfirmed expectations create a state of dissonance or a psychological discomfort (Yi, 1990). According to this theory, the existence of dissonance produces pressures for its reduction, which could be achieved by adjusting the perceived disparity. This theory holds that "post-exposure ratings are primarily a function of the expectation level because the task of recognising disconfirmation is believed to be psychologically uncomfortable.

Thus, consumers are posited to perceptually distort expectation-discrepant performance so as to coincide with their prior expectation level" (Oliver, 1977). For instance, if a disparity exists between product expectations and product performance, consumers may have a psychological tension and try to reduce it by changing their perception of the product (Yi, 1990).

Applying the Comparison Level Theory to the confirmation/disconfirmation process, LaTour & Peat found that experience-based standards or norms play a role as a baseline for comparisons in consumers' satisfaction judgments. They found that situationally induced expectations had little effect on the customer satisfaction, while expectations based on prior experiences were the major determinant of customer satisfaction.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A sample of 120 literate individuals was randomly selected from the population of numerous customers of selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos, Nigeria. A structured questionnaire, divided into two parts, A and B, was used in collecting the required data from the respondents. Part A contained items on demographic variables, and Part B contained items to measure the active variables of (Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction), Customer Request, and Food Delivery Cycle Time. The questionnaire items were measured on a 5-Point Likert-Type Scale from Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 to Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, while the descriptive statistical techniques of Simple Percentile and Regression were used to analyse the data.

Results and Analysis

Hypothesis I

H₀ Service quality consistency does not have a significant relationship with sales volume in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Model Summary for service quality consistency and sales volume

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.336 ^a	.113	.105	.484

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service Quality Consistency

The result, as presented in Table 1, indicates that there is a weak positive relationship ($r=0.336$) between service quality consistency and sales volume. The coefficient of determination of 11.3% affirmed that about 11.3 of% variation in sales volume at the selected food outlets could be attributed to quality consistency. However, the addition of any other explanatory variables to the model will only result in about 10.5% variation in sales volume.

Table 2: ANOVA^a for service quality consistency and sales volume

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.520	1	3.520	15.025	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.646	118	.234		
	Total	31.167	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Sales Volume

b. Predictors: (Constant), Service Quality Consistency

Furthermore, the F-value is 15.025 with a p-value (0.000) less than the 5% significance level. This affirmed that the model is adequate and sufficient in relating the dependent and the independent variable. Hence, the test is significant.

Table 3: Coefficients^a for service quality consistency and sales volume

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.153	.707		10.112	.000
	Food Quality Consistency	.061	.016	.336	3.876	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Service Quality Consistency

Moreover, the regression coefficient for quality consistency is 0.061 with a standard error of 0.016. The t-value is 3.876 with a p-value of 0.000.

This result confirms that for every unit increase in consistency in the provision of quality foods to the customers, there will be about a 6.1% increase in sales volume. Since the test is significant, we then accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that service quality consistency does have a significant relationship and effect on the sales volume of selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Hypothesis II

H₀ There is no significant relationship between staff etiquette and customer purchase intention in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Table 4: Model Summary of Staff etiquette and customer purchase intention

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.766 ^a	.586	.583	.302

a. Predictors: (Constant), Staff etiquette

The result of the analysis indicates a very strong positive relationship between staff etiquette and customer purchase intention, with a correlation coefficient of 0.766, and about 58.6% variation in customer purchase intention could be attributed to staff etiquette.

Table 5: ANOVA of Staff etiquette and customer purchase intention

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.228	1	15.228	167.320	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.739	118	.091		
	Total	25.967	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Intention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Staff etiquette

From the ANOVA (table 5), the result revealed an F-value of 167.320 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 5% significance level. Hence, the model is adequate and sufficient in relating Staff etiquette and customer purchase intention. The test is significant.

Table 6: Coefficients of Staff etiquette and customer purchase intention

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-.796	.396		-2.009	.047
	Staff Etiquette	.115	.009	.766	12.935	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Intention

The constant value is negative (Table 6), which is a point that in the absence of staff etiquette, there is likely to be lower customer purchase intention in the shopping mall under consideration. In addition, the regression coefficient for staff etiquette is positive with a value of 0.115 and a standard error of 0.009. Also, the t-value is 12.935 with p-value (0.000) less than the 5% significance level.

This result implies that as staff etiquette increases, there will be about 11.5% increase in customer purchase intention at the selected eateries and restaurants. Since the test is significant, we then conclude by accepting the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between staff etiquette and customer purchase intention.

Discussion

The responses from the respondents revealed that most of the respondents affirmed that there is service quality consistency in selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, with confirmation that the staff of the company serve food in an orderly manner and that they treat customers well such that there is always an influence, such that customers wish to come back the second time.

This, however, corroborates the Dissonance Theory, which posits that ‘post-exposure ratings are primarily a function of the expectation level because the task of recognising disconfirmation is believed to be psychologically uncomfortable.

This finding also conforms with the Comparison Level Theory that ‘situationally induced expectations had little effect on customer satisfaction, while expectations based on prior experiences were the major determinant of customer satisfaction.

Nevertheless, the study was confined to Lagos State; it may enjoy limited generalisation due to location, population characteristics and sample size.

Conclusion

The study investigates the relationship between service quality delivery and customer satisfaction among customers of selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The simple random sampling method was used to select 120 individuals who are customers of selected food outlets in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

The research design was a survey design with a self-structured questionnaire as the main instrument for data collection. Data analysis instruments were Percentages, Correlation and Regression statistical techniques for data analysis. However, the findings of the study revealed that service quality consistency does have a significant relationship and effect on the sales volume of food outlets ($r = 0.336$, $p < 0.05$) and that there is a significant relationship between staff etiquette and customer purchase intention ($r = 0.766$, $p < 0.05$).

Recommendations

Nevertheless, from a managerial perspective, it is important for operators and owners of food outlets to develop appropriate induction programs and provide ongoing training on the various attributes of responsiveness to strengthen employees' ability to improve customer service. Although easy to suggest, instilling these qualities in the frontline personnel and gaining their commitment can be challenging.

However, if full-service food outlets want to deliver high levels of customer satisfaction, they could periodically track staff performance to measure the level of responsiveness. By doing so, supervisors and owners of food outlets can design targeted training programs that enhance customer-service skills in active listening, empathy, complaints handling, role playing, teamwork and collaboration, upselling and closing-thought techniques. Again, modern food safety techniques must be put in place to enhance proper food handling, food storage and hygiene through integration of technology.

Furthermore, employees of food outlet owners must introduce training programs that will enhance excellent service and waiting time, such as between 5-10 minutes for a table, 15-30 minutes for food preparation and 30 minutes for a table in busy environments. These techniques will, however, assist in developing an appealing menu, excellent service quality at all times, which will aid in the appropriate identification and anticipation of the needs of customers, ensure consistency of service quality with customer orders, strengthen periodic staff training to enhance good staff etiquette and service lead-time.

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